

THE ROLE OF EDUCATION IN REVAMPING SOCIO-ECONOMIC GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT IN THE NORTH EAST, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This research work examined the role of education in revamping socio-economic growth and development in the north east. Looking at the abundant natural and human resources the country is endowed with, one will wonder why the north-east is still living in abject poverty, bedeviled by various crimes and insurgency. Base on this, the study looked at the current educational status in the region under study and its impact on socio-economic growth and development. To do this, three objectives were formulated to guide the study. The broad objective of the study is to assess current status of education and its impact on the prevailing crimes and insurgency as well as on socio-economic growth and development. One specific objective is to examine the role of education in revamping socio-economic growth and development in the area of study. The study was conducted using survey design; the population of the study constitutes educational planners, policy makers, school managers, parents and students in the North East zone of Nigeria. The sampling technique was purposive sampling technique to select two states that are most hit by poverty and crimes (Borno and Yobe) and random sampling method to select respondents. The sample size is 400 respondents, that is, eighty respondents from educational planners, policy makers, school managers, parents and students each making two hundred. A ten item questionnaire base on two points likert scale was used to get opinions of respondents. Inferential and descriptive statistics was used to analyze the data using SPSS package

Introduction

Nigeria, particularly the North-East zone, is going through crises and confusion socially,

academically, politically and psychologically as a result of insurgency, kidnapping, herds - killers, fraudsters and many crimes of varying degrees. These have led to immense suffering, trauma,

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poor level of education and high poverty level in the region. Generally, the role of education is to foster human and socio-economic development through educating citizens, developing economic thinking and behavior, awakening cultural consciousness and interests among others (Taiwo, 2010). These done successfully, lay a pace for socio-economic development. Taiwo reiterated that when education is combined with socio-economic development, it will address the basic human needs in Nigeria in general. When the basic human needs are met, rate of crimes and insurgency will be minimized. The federal ministry of Education (2003) in its report on education policy and man power supply stated that in the present technological era, a major function of education is to produce knowledge based workforce for national development, any attempt to remove education from a system leads to the collapse of that system. Socio economic development in the North-East is at a very low level due to the activities of insurgency which include among other things burning down of schools and killing teachers. The National Commission for Colleges of Education (1992) in Wakawa (2011) and Todaro and Smith, (2015).assert that, education is a deliberate and organized effort to initiate the learner into a way of thinking, believing and into a core of norms, values, skills and techniques considered desirable for developmental purposes in his/her society, by this definition, it is clear that education is a tool for transforming individuals and nations for socio-economic growth and development translating into good health care

services, stable economic growth, infrastructural development, good governance, well organized political system and selfless services among others.

Education is the light that shows the way by removing the darkness of ignorance, the salt that gives the taste of life, the medicine that cures and the key that unlocks doors of self-discovery (Lawal, 2006). Education teaches individuals to accept and face reality in the society, it breaks the shell of ignorance and opens that of self - discovery. It is the right tool to challenge individuals for better productivity. The success of any society depends to large extent on the youths which are the pillars and most productive segment of every society, their ability to learn to tolerate, accommodate, respect, share, establish friendships and dialogue among all ethnic, political and religious groups with ease come from the right type of education (education that works for all). The education system in the area of study has been mutilated and destroyed by insurgency and various crimes prevalent in the area. UNICEF (2019) reported that as a result of violent crisis on the region, relentless kidnappings, capture of towns, bombings and gun attacks on the people, Socio - economic growth and development is stagnated.

Socio - economic growth and development is the process of economic and social transformation that improves the conditions of the people of a particular place. For the North - East to revamp her socio - economic growth and development and remain relevant and effective, education should and most be a vital pivot in the march to

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safe and sustainable socio-economic development. As the saying goes, no nation can develop above the level of her education system, therefore, concerted effort to transform education in the north is required. People should be trained to achieve self- fulfillment through hard work and merit, shunning evil vices and greed, begin to live for others, look at national interest as superseding personal interest and expend their excess energies in doing worthwhile endeavors.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the unquestionable abundant human and natural resources the nation Nigeria has, the North East region is still living in abject poverty as a result of insurgency, kidnapping and abductions among others. The crime rate is very high and development in this area has been at a stand- still for years. So many research evidences have pointed to poverty and low level of education as major key contributors to crimes and insurgency particularly in the north-east. It is against this background that this study intends to examine the role of education in minimizing crimes and poverty thereby revamping socio-economic growth and development in the region, with the hope and believe that when functional education is given to the masses, crimes and insurgency will be minimized.

Objectives

The broad objective of this paper is to assess the current status of education and its impact on the prevailing crimes and insurgency as well as on

socio-economic growth and development. The specific objectives are to:

1. Examine the relationship between education and socio-economic growth and development in the north-east.
2. Assess the role of education in revamping socio - economic growth and development in the north-east.
3. Examine the role of education in minimizing insurgency and crimes

Literature Review

This section will review research evidences, opinions and empirical studies related to the topic under study. It will define concepts related to the topic and explain theories on which the topic stands.

Concept of Education

Education is defined by the national policy on education (2004) as an instrument for national development and for acquisition of knowledge and skills that will make one a better person who can contribute meaningfully to the development of self and the society. Another similar definition was proposed by Balarabe, cited in Wakawa (2011) as the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values and norms that are useful to the individual and the society where the person lives.

Education is considered a bedrock on which all forms of development take place, it is a builder if properly acquired and destroyer if otherwise. It builds in the individual tolerance, selfless service, improves productive capacity of individual and society and their political, social, economic and scientific institutions (Danjuma 2022). He added that it involves cultivating the mind and instilling

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values that enable individuals to distinguish between right and wrong. It is a process of acquiring skills and knowledge to help one in relating acceptably with others in the society.

Over the years, the standard of education has indicated a gross departure in terms of usability and quality from the earlier years (1960 - 2000s). These can be seen through (1) poor performance in standardized examinations. For Instance, studies by the Programmed for International student Assessment (PISA) reported that the performance of 15 year old students in reading mathematics and science has declined in many countries between 2018 and 2022. (2) Lack of critical thinking and problem -solving skills. The World Economic Forum highlighted the importance of developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills in students, citing a survey of employers who ranked these skills as essential for modern workforce which is lacking in most products of modern school systems. (3) Reduced economic competitiveness. A report by the Mckinsey Global Institute highlighted the link between education and economic growth, citing evidence that countries with high performing education systems tend to have stronger economies. Other indicators are: - Low literacy and numeracy rates, limited creativity and innovation and declining grades in standardized examinations among many others. These indicators of negative shift in quality of education have been linked to outdated curriculum and teaching methods, inadequate teacher training, insufficient resources and poor infrastructure and many others. The social and

economic development of nations is fundamentally an educational process in which people learn to create new institutions, use new technologies, cope with their environment and alter their patterns of behavior. Education improves the capabilities of the individuals and the capacity of institutions, and become a catalyst for all the interrelated economic, social, cultural and demographic changes that are defined as national development (Balarabe, 2009). From this, it can be deduced that education has a vital role in all forms of development in all societies, the north-east inclusive.

Socio - Economic Growth and Development

Socio - economic growth is a complex and multi - dimensional processes that aims at improving the economic and social well - being of individuals and communities (Todaro and Smith, 2015). It is the process of economic and social transformation that improves the conditions of the people of a particular place. Nigeria is a nation blessed with abundant human and natural resources enough to strive for heights and lead the World. Batunde (2002) posited that Nigeria has abundant economic promises, it is a large nation endowed with a variety of natural and human resources and her people are industrious, venturous and economically responsive. According to him, education was central to development planning strategy at both regional and Federal levels initially. Even though there were fewer institutions of learning and few elites, they rendered selfless services; then the

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economy was moderately stable with agriculture as the main source. According to Balarabe (2009), in 1960 after the independence, international reports rated Nigeria along with nations like India, Brazil and Malaysia as emerging nations that will attain development status in the decades to come. Education was even referred to as an instrument ‘par excellence’ for effecting national development.

Economic growth is measured by increase in Gross Development Product which reflects the total value of goods and services produced in a country and are linked to improved living standards (Barro, 1996). According to him, education is a fundamental right as it enhances human capital and active participation in economic activities. As a result of improper education, the rich human and material resources of the nation have not been channeled appropriately towards the education that transforms living the masses in chaos and abject poverty especially the north-east. The World development report (2006 and 2007) that the level of eradicating extreme poverty and hunger per population living below a dollar per day in Nigeria is 70.8%, of Brazil is 8% and that of Malaysia is <2%. The Gross Domestic Product has dropped beyond the projected expectation at 3.4 percent by 2025 (African Development Bank, 2024). According to this report, investment in education is poor and poverty remains high with 63 percent of Nigerians still multidimensionally poor. The same report indicated that 18 out of the 36 states recorded poverty levels that are above the national average, Borno and Yobe are

inclusive. Citing Odour, (2024), Nigeria faces rising financial costs in global markets, with its 30-year bond trading at a double digit yield of 11-11 percent in 2023 (10.58 percent in April 2024). This is not a good indicator of socio-economic growth and development. The rising poverty level in the north east is alarming, according to report by the National Bureau of Statistics (2023), poverty rate in this region is 78.8 percent and one factor responsible for this is limited access to quality education. Socio economic growth and development requires the talents, wisdom, energies and sacrifices of all individuals which can only be achieved through education which facilitates socio-economic development. The following theories buttressed the topic under study: (1) Education and human Development theory stated that education is seen as a key factor in promoting human development including improved health, well-being and civics engagement. (2) Compatibility Approach stated that education provides individuals with skills and knowledge necessary to participate in the workforce and contribute to economic development. (3) Economic Growth Theory which emphasized that education is a critical driver of economic growth as it provides the human capital necessary to drive innovation, entrepreneurship and productivity.

Methodology

The methodology of this work is the skeletal framework of how the study will be conducted. The design of the study is the survey research method, aimed at gathering data from both primary and secondary sources. The population

Dr Mercy Bathli Wakawa and Mohammed Ubaida Talba

of the study constitutes all educational planners, policy makers, school managers, parents and students across the North - East zone. The sampling technique used is purposive and random sampling techniques to select two states that are socio-economically backward (Borno and Yobe) from the six states in the north-east geo-political zone and 400 respondents from across these states. Data was generated using self

- constructed six item questionnaire base on two points likert scale (Agree / Disagree) to get opinions of respondents. Descriptive and Inferential statistics was used to analyze the data using SPSS package.

Results/findings

The findings of this study are presented here in a tabular form:

1. Low level of education is equated with low socio-economic growth and development

No Respondents	of Agree	Percentage	Disagree	Percentage	Total
400	272	68	128	32	100%

Source: Field work, 2025.

Table one shows that 68% of the respondents agreed that low level of education is equated poor

socio-economic growth and development while 32% attribute poor socio-economic development to other factors other than education.

Table 2: Education improves individual and community lives in all dimensions.

No Respondents	of Agree	Percentage	Disagree	Percentage	Total
400	326	59	164	41	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2025

From table two, 236, that is 59% respondents agreed that education improves lives of individuals and community in all dimensions while 164, that is 41% disagreed that education

transforms lives of individuals but rather attributed improvement and transformation of lives of individuals and community to other factors.

Table 3: Functional education leads to transformation of individual lives and socio-economic growth and development.

No Respondents	of Agree	Percentage	Disagree	Percentage	Total
400	275	71	125	29	100%

Source: Fieldwork, 2025.

Table three shows that out of 400 participants, 275 that is 71% agreed that functional education leads to transformation of individual lives and

socio-economic growth and development while 125, that is 29% respondents disagreed.

Table 4: Adequate knowledge and skills are vital in harnessing resources in one's environment.

No Respondents	of Agree	Percentage	Disagree	Percentage	Total
400	275	71%	125	29%	100%

Source: Field work, 2025.

Table four shows that out of 400 respondents, 215 that is 54% agreed that adequate knowledge and skills are vital in harnessing resources in

one's environment while 185 that is 46% disagreed and attributed socio-economic growth and development to other factors.

Table 5: Crimes and insurgency thrive more in less educated communities leading to apathy.

No Respondents	of Agree	Percentage	Disagree	Percentage	Total
400	327	82%	73	18%	100%

Source: Field work, 2025.

Table five shows that out of 400 respondents, 327, that is 82% agreed that Crimes and insurgency thrive more in less educated

communities leading to feeling of apathy while 73, that is 18% disagreed and attributed crimes and insurgency to other factors.

Table 6: low level of education encourages unequal distribution of resources and opportunities leading to crimes and insurgency.

No Respondents	of Agree	Percentage	Disagree	Percentage	Total
400	359	90%	41	10%	100%

Source: Field work, 2025.

Table six shows that out of 400 respondents, 359, that is 90% agreed that low level of education encourages unequal distribution of resources and opportunities leading to crimes and insurgency. While 41, that is 10% disagreed.

The data collected was analyzed using simple percentage which led to the below findings. Table one indicated that 78% of the respondent agreeing that low level of education is equated with low socio-economic growth and development. This means where education is not embraced, the aftermath shows poor socio-

Discussion of Major Findings

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economic growth and development. This coincides with the report by the National Bureau of Statistics (2023), which emphasized that the rising poverty level in the North East is alarming, (poverty rate in this region is 78.8 percent) and one factor responsible for this is limited access to quality education. This is also in line with a report by the Mckinsey Global Institute which highlighted the link between education and economic growth, citing evidence that countries with high performing education systems tend to have stronger economies. This means, socio economic growth and development requires the talents, wisdom, energies and sacrifices of all individuals channeled appropriately through education.

Table two showed that greater percent of the respondents (59%) believed that education is a tool that improves individual and community lives. Through education, people acquire knowledge and skills that lead to self- sufficiency and reliant contributing their quota meaningfully to socio-economic growth and development. This finding buttressed the national policy on education (2004) which sees education as an instrument for national development and for acquisition of knowledge and skills that will make one a better person who can contribute meaningfully to the development of self and the society where the person lives. It also supported the findings of Balarabe, (2009) which stated that social and economic development of nations is fundamentally an educational process in which people learn to create new institutions, use new technologies,

cope with their environment and alter their patterns of behavior. Education improves the capabilities of the individuals and the capacity of institutions, and become a catalyst for all the interrelated economic, social, cultural and demographic changes that are defined as national development,

Table three shows that 71% of the respondents agreed that functional education leads to transformation of individual lives and socio-economic growth and development while 125, that is 29% respondents disagreed and attributed transformation of lives to other factors. Table four showed that 54% of the respondents agreed that adequate knowledge and skills are vital in harnessing resources in one's environment which lends credit to the findings of the World Economic Forum which highlighted the importance of developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills in students. When equipped with critical thinking and problem solving skills, socio-economic growth and development comes with ease. Table five indicated that 82% agreed that crimes and insurgency thrive more in less educated communities leading to feeling of apathy and helplessness which negate socio-economic growth and development.

Table six shows that 90% of the respondents agreed that low level of education encourages unequal distribution of resources and opportunities leading to crimes and insurgency. This is in line with the position of UNICEF (2019) which stated that the education system in the north-east has been mutilated and destroyed by

Dr Mercy Bathli Wakawa and Mohammed Ubaida Talba

insurgency and various crimes, that as a result of violent crisis on the region, relentless kidnappings, capture of towns, bombings and gun attacks on the people, Socio - economic growth and development is stagnated.

Summarily, the study has shown beyond reasonable doubt that education is a prerequisite of meaningful socio-economic growth and development particularly in the north-east geopolitical zone.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is concluded that there is no meaningful socio-economic growth and development without proper acquisition of knowledge and skills which is the process of education. It also indicated that

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where there is predominance of illiterates, crimes and insurgency thrive more.

Recommendation

Base on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are put forward:

1. To revamp socio-economic development in the north-east, more resources should be mobilized and invested in the education sector.
2. To minimize crimes and insurgency in the zone, parents, policy makers, government, philanthropists most all come together to improve education sector in terms of quality and accessibility.
3. Further studies should be conducted in this area by prospective researchers.

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Dr Mercy Bathli Wakawa and Mohammed Ubaida Talba